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IDENTIFICATION AND MANAGEMENT OF POSTPARTUM WOMEN ASSOCIATED WITH PSYCHIATRIC COOMORBIDITY AND ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Postpartum psychiatric disorders are the common conditions that are frequently missed by health care team but have significant negative impact on parenting capacities which in turn results in negative outcome of child cognitive and emotional developmental progress. The main aim of the study is to identify and manage the postpartum women who are associated with psychiatric illness and to assess the effectiveness of the management. The patients were identified using different scales like HARS, EPDS, PHQ. The study revealed that the postpartum psychiatric illness like anxiety and depression was majorly in age group 20-25, with incidence rate 43.33% which is higher. The study showed positive outcomes for intervention. Hence this study is useful for clinicians and other healthcare providers to identify the patients at risk and treating them early. We also conclude that awareness of such diseases regarding symptoms and progression through educational programmes will help in better maternal and child postnatal care.

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INTRODUCTION

A postpartum period or postnatal period is the period beginning immediately after the birth of a child and extending for about six weeks. The World Health Organization (WHO) describes the postnatal period as the most critical and yet the most neglected phase in the lives of mothers and babies; most deaths occur during the postnatal period^[1]. Women during pregnancy and postpartum period were more liable to the psychiatric disorders^[2]. Parental meagre care during prenatal period and other somatic illness will lead the patient more susceptible to postpartum psychiatric illness and their complications^[2, 3, 9, 10, 11]. The major focus of postpartum care is ensuring that the mother is healthy and capable of taking care of her new born equipped with all the information she needs about breastfeeding, reproductive health and contraception, and the imminent life adjustment. But the focus on other possible disorders during this period is less.

Comorbidities in postpartum period:

- venous thromboembolism
- deepvein thrombosis
- pulmonary embolus
- depression
- anxiety
- bipolar disorder
- anemia
- panic disorder
- DM(gestational diabetes)
- Obsessive compulsive disorder

Approximately 25% - 85% of postpartum women will experience the "blues" for a few days. Between 7% and 17% may experience clinical depression, with a higher risk among those women with a history of clinical depression. Rarely, in 1 in 1,000 cases, women experience a psychotic episode, again with a higher risk among those women with pre-existing mental illness^[4].

Postpartum anxiety:

While any new mom can develop postpartum anxiety, those who are especially vulnerable include women with a personal or family history of anxiety or previous experience with depression, certain symptoms of PMS (such as feeling weepy or agitated), eating disorders, or obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD).

Postnatal anxiety is the broad term used to refer to a range of conditions that have a number of common symptoms including: feelings of fear and worry which begin to 'take over' your thinking, feeling irritable, restless, tense or constantly 'on edge' racing heart/strong palpitations – sometimes panic attacks^[5].

State anxiety was measured among breast-feeding women by the State Trait Anxiety Inventory before hospital discharge and at 1 month postpartum. Breast-feeding experience and knowledge were assessed by focused questions and confidence by the Breastfeeding Confidence Scale. Breast-feeding performance measures included breast-feeding immediately after delivery; formula supplementation in the hospital; full, exclusive breast-feeding; and breast-feeding termination at 1 month postpartum^[5].

Past studies were less focussed on postpartum anxiety when compared to depression as the incidence of anxiety is low. But still postpartum anxiety shows negative impact on both maternal and child health so it is clinically important to identify the patients who at risk of developing anxiety which results in improving perinatal care.

Postpartum depression:

Postpartum depression or postnatal depression is the major area which requires further research for both identification and treatment. It is well defined in accordance with DSM-IV criteria for major depressive disorder^[3, 3(1,2)]. Women with postpartum depression have been experienced with certain consequences like difficulty in infant feeding and the incomplete mother and infant relationship, child can exhibit poor and unhealthy relationships, decreased activities, impaired cognitive functions, decreased orientation^[4,4(1,6,10)] etc. This is because only in early periods of postpartum the mother could establish a good mother infant relation^[6].

Various etiological factors will contribute for the depression. The severity of postpartum depression will varies according to the risk factors and etiological factors associated. Until date various previous studies shown majorly some social factors are largely, associated with the postpartum depression followed by biological, emotional and obstetric factors. Even history of psychiatric illness, delivery complications, maternity blues will also contribute to some extent^[6, 12, 13, 14, 15]. However the postpartum depression will not occurred with any one factor but many factors will require for the patient to develop the postpartum depression.

Management of the postpartum depression is usually made through psychotherapy for mild to moderate depression. Combination of psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy showed better results with the severe depression. If a particular underlying risk factor was identified the treatment should be aimed at that underlying cause^[4]. Pharmacotherapy includes antidepressants and hormonal therapy with Estrogen and progesterone has also shown positive results to some extent^[6].

Postpartum psychosis:

Postpartum psychosis is a rare psychiatric emergency in which symptoms of high mood and racing thoughts (mania), depression, severe confusion, loss of inhibition, paranoia, hallucinations and delusions set in, beginning suddenly in the first two weeks after delivery. The symptoms vary and can change quickly^[7]. The most severe symptoms last from 2 to 12 weeks, and recovery takes 6 months to a year^[7].

About half of women who experience it have no risk factors; but women with a prior history of mental illness, especially bipolar disorder, a history of prior episodes of postpartum psychosis, or a family history are at a higher risk. It is not a formal diagnosis, but is widely used to describe a condition that appears to occur in about 1 in a 1000 pregnancies. 25 to 50% of women with a history of mental illness experience postpartum psychosis^[8] around 37% of women with bipolar disorder have a severe postpartum episode. Women with a prior episode of postpartum psychosis have about a 30% risk of having another episode in the next pregnancy.

For a woman with no history of mental illness who has a close relative (a mother or sister) who had postpartum psychosis, the risk is about 3%^[8]. There may be a genetic component; while mutations in chromosome 16 and in specific genes involved in serotonergic, hormonal, and inflammatory pathways have been identified, none had been confirmed as of 2014.

Management:

In most cases hospital admission is necessary. Antipsychotic drugs and mood stabilizing drugs such as lithium are typically administered but is not clear if mood stabilizers can be titrated to a high enough level quickly enough to be effective^[7,8]. Electroconvulsive therapy may be considered, especially if there is a high risk of suicide^[7]. The main aim of the study is to identify and manage the postpartum women who are associated with psychiatric illness and to assess the effectiveness of the management.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A prospective observational study was conducted for 6 months in the Obstetric and gynecology wards, Rajeev Gandhi Institute of medical sciences, Kadapa.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- ✓ Women in the postpartum period aging between 20-30 years.
- ✓ Patients with or without any past psychiatric illness.
- ✓ Women willing to participate in the study.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- ✓ Women more than 6 weeks after delivery.

STUDY MATERIALS:

- 📄 Patient data collection proforma (Annexure-I)
- 📄 Patient information consent form (Annexure-II)
- 📄 The Hamilton rating scale for anxiety (Annexure-III)
- 📄 Edinburgh postnatal depression scale (Annexure-IV)
- 📄 Patient health related questionnaire (Annexure-V)

Method of the study:

Literature review was done on the related postpartum psychiatric complications and a protocol was designed to conduct the study according to the institutional ethics and then submitted to the ethics committee to get approval. The OBG wards were visited on daily basis and 30 postpartum women were included in the study as they fulfil the study inclusion criteria. The details of the selected subjects such as demographics, past history of both medical and psychiatric illness etc were obtained from patient's medical charts and their personal interviews. Then the patients were screened for anxiety, depression and psychosis by using scales the Hamilton rating scale for anxiety, Edinburgh postnatal depression scale, Patient health related questionnaire respectively. Then based on the score the patients were categorised into patients with associated psychiatric illness and not associated psychiatric illness. The patients who were identified with the presence of any anxiety or depression were subjected to psychiatric intervention based on their severity of associated psychiatric illness. Then the patients were reviewed after 1 month and assessed with the same scales and the scores were observed before and after.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Collected data will be analysed by using appropriate statistical analytical technique (t-test ...) was performed to calculate the P- value for the purpose of comparison of results by using software mainly t-test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A total of 30 postpartum women were included in the study as they fulfil the inclusion criteria. Data was analysed and the patients were categorised into various groups based on different criteria like age, presence of past psychiatric illness, literacy, complication of pregnancy and severity of the associated illness. The results were as follows.

DISTRIBUTION OF THE PATIENTS BASED ON AGE:

Age was considered because the past studies indicate that early and late pregnancies were risk factors for the development of postpartum psychiatric illness. Among 30 patients majority of the patients i.e., 73.33% (22) were in the age group 20-25 followed by 23.33% (7) in age group 26-30 and 1 patient 3.33% in age group 31-35. This is represented in table: 01. As the study was conducted in urban area majority of postpartum women were in the age group 20-25.

Table: 01, Distribution of patient based on age.

AGE	No. Of Patients	percentage
20-25	22	73.33%
26-30	7	23.33%
31-35	1	3.33%

DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON PRESENCE OF PAST PSYCHIATRIC HISTORY:

The presence of past psychiatric history will make the women more prone to psychiatric illness during postpartum period. But as we observed the patients who were included in the study do not have any past psychiatric illness.

DISTRIBUTION BASED PATIENTS BASED ON COMPLICATION OF PREGNANCY:

The patients with complicated pregnancies were more prone to psychological illness as there are emotional factors like fear, stress, worry about the safety of child and delivery which will alter the psychological behaviour of the patient. In our study the majority of patients had no complications, followed by Oligohydromnios, Pregnancy induced Hypertension, Eclampsia, ectopic pregnancy which was indicated in the fig:01.

Fig: 01, Distribution based on complication of pregnancy.**DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS BASED ON LITERACY:**

Literacy will have indirect contribution to the psychological behaviour of the patient as the literate patients have more awareness of pregnancies and postpartum and their complications and can overcome these by taking preventive measures when compared to illiterate patient. In our study 56.67% of patients were illiterate and 43.33% patients were literate which is represented in figure as follows

Fig: 02, Distribution based on literacy.

DISTRIBUTION BASED ON SEVERITY OF ANXIETY WITH RESPECT TO AGE:

The patient population was categorised into mild, moderate, severe and no anxiety. We found that 19 (63.33%) patients among study population had no anxiety, followed by 8 (26.67%) with mild anxiety and 3 (10.00%) with moderate anxiety. Here in our study we did not identify any patient with severe anxiety. Whatever the severity mild moderate or no anxiety was majorly seen in age group 20-25 which is represented in tabular form and figure as follows.

Table: 02, Distribution of patients based on severity of anxiety with respect to age.

Age	Mild	Moderate	no	Total
20-25	7	2	13	22
26-30	1	1	5	7
31-35	0	0	1	1

Fig: 03, Distribution of patients based on severity of anxiety with respect to age.

DISTRIBUTION BASED ON SEVERITY OF DEPRESSION WITH RESPECT TO AGE:

Among 30 postpartum patients, 23 patients had no depression and 7 patients had minimal depression. Our study population were not reported mild, moderate and severe depression. But past studies indicates the depression was more prevalent than anxiety. This difference in the results may be due to less study population. The severity of depression with respect to age was represented in table: 03 and Fig: 04.

Table: 03, Distribution based on severity of depression with respect to age.

Age	No	Minimal	Total	Percentage
20-25	18	4	22	73.33%
26-30	4	3	7	23.33%
31-35	1	0	1	3.33%

Fig: 04, Distribution based on severity of depression with respect to age.

In our study, among 30 postpartum patients only 13 patients were found to be with psychiatric comorbidity. And these patients were subjected to psychiatric intervention. As no patients were found with severe anxiety or depression, pharmacological intervention was not done in our study. For mild, minimal and moderate severe patients non-pharmacological therapy like psychotherapy and educational therapy was provided. Later after one month the patients were reviewed and again assessed with scales to evaluate the effectiveness of intervention. Later the scores before and after intervention were compared statistically. The statistical comparison was represented in table: 04.

Table: 04, Average scores of each scale at base line and follow-up.

Sl.No.	HARS		EPDS		BPRS		PHRQ	
	Baseline	Follow-up	baseline	Follow-up	Baseline	Follow-up	Baseline	Follow-up
1.	13	10	13	12	17	15	7	7
2.	24	22	9	9	20	20	4	4
3.	10	10	11	11	57	54	9	8
4.	11	10	8	8	42	40	4	4
5.	22	22	18	18	52	50	4	4
6.	17	17	8	8	23	23	4	4
7.	14	13	17	17	29	29	6	6
8.	10	10	7	7	42	40	5	4
9.	13	12	11	11	28	27	3	3
10.	20	8	8	6	23	35	2	5
11.	16	20	14	8	55	22	7	2
12.	8	16	6	15	37	57	5	8
13.	19	17	21	20	32	31	5	5
Average	15.153	14.384	11.6153	11.538	35.153	34.0769	5.000	4.923
p-value	0.6956		0.9666		0.7459		0.8884	

Even though the result has no statistical difference, the average scores were decreased from baseline to follow-up which indicates the positive outcome in patients upon intervention. As the psychological illness takes a long time to be cured further follow-ups of patients was recommended to get complete satisfactory positive outcome.

It was also found that incidence postpartum psychiatric illness in our study population was not more but we strongly recommend to screen the postpartum women to identify the patients with risk of developing these illness. It in turn helps for better care for the women and as well to the child.

CONCLUSION

Psychiatric comorbidity is common in postpartum period and can be detected as early as first week after delivery. Past studies primarily focus on comorbid depression however emerging and other study indicates that anxiety is as important as depression. Anxiety and depression disorders amplify symptoms of some medical illness and worsen clinical outcomes. The measures that we used to assess psychiatric illness do not always conform with DSM-IV, so differential diagnosis should be further considered to make appropriate clinical decision. It needs larger sample to generalize the finding of our study. We tried to find the relation and the reason what causing and found a good positive response from patients after performing an intervention based on the severity of associated comorbidity. As the incidence was high it is the responsibility of the clinicians to identify the patients who are risk of developing psychiatric illness and treating them for the purpose of better patient care.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

We do not have any conflict of interest.

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I thank my Parents who have been the emblem of love and for their encouragement. It is with their support and guidance; I walk through the path of success.

REFERENCES

1. WHO, "WHO recommendations on post natal care of the mother and new born," retrieved 22 december 2014.
2. Oriana Vesga-Lo'pez, MD; Carlos Blanco, MD, PhD; Katherine Keyes, MPH; Mark Olfson, MD, MPH; Bridget F. Grant, PhD, PhD; Deborah S. Hasin, PhD "Psychiatric Disorders in Pregnant and Postpartum Women in the United States" arch gen psychiatry/vol 65 (no. 7), july 2008.
3. Kelly RH, Russo J, Katon W. Somatic complaints among pregnant women cared for in obstetrics: normal pregnancy or depressive and anxiety symptom amplification revisited: Gen Hosp Psychiatry. 2001;23(3):107-113.
4. Sara Thurgood, BS, Daniel M. Avery, MD, Lloyd Williamson, MD. Postpartum depression: American journal of clinical medicine, / vol-6, 2009.
5. John R Britton et.al., Postpartum anxiety and breastfeeding A journal of reproductive medicine, 52(8), pg no 689-695, 2007
6. Peter J Cooper and Lynne murray, Archives of Disease in Childhood 1997;77:97-101
7. Jones, Dazzan, LM, "bipolar disorder, affective psychosis and schizophrenia in pregnancy and the postpartum period, 384(9956),pg no 1789-99, 15 nov 2014.
8. Postpartum psychosis, " royal college of psychiatrists, retrieved 27 october 2016.
9. Heron J, O'Connor TG, Evans J, Golding J, Glover V. The course of anxiety and depression through pregnancy and the postpartum in a community sample. J Affect Disord. 2004;80(1):65-73.
10. Stowe ZN, Hostetter AL, Newport DJ. The onset of postpartum depression: implications for clinical screening in obstetrical and primary care.AmJ Obstet Gynecol. 2005;192(2):522-526.
11. Kelly RH, Danielsen BH, Golding JM, Anders TF, Gilbert WM, Zatzick DF. Adequacy of prenatal care among women with psychiatric diagnoses giving birth in California in 1994 and 1995. Psychiatr Serv. 1999;50(12):1584-1590.
12. Murray L, Cartwright W. The role of obstetric factors in postpartum depression. J Reprod Inf Psychol 1993; 11: 215-9.
13. O'Hara, MW, Schlechte JA, Lewis DA, Varner MW. A controlled prospective study of postpartum mood disorders: psychological, environmental, and hormonal variables. J Abnorm Psychol 1991;100: 63-73.
14. Kendell RE. Emotional and physical factors in the genesis of puerperal mental disorders. J Psychosom Res 1985;29:3-11.
15. Appleby L, Gregoire A, Platz C, Martin P, Kumar R. Screening women for high risk of postnatal depression. J Psychosom Res 1994; 38: 539-45.

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